

←-mercaptobenzothiazole has been used for the first time for Re analysis.

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Mercury Tris-[2,4,6-(2-hydroxy-4-sulpho-1-naphthylazo)]-s-triazine Trisodium Salt Complex in the Spectrophotometric Determination of Thiosulphate, Thiourea and Thiosemicarbazide Ions through Ligand Exchange Reaction†

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TRIS-[2,4,6-(2-hydroxy-4-sulpho-1-naphthylazo)]-s-triazine trisodium salt (THT)^{1,2}, a water soluble heterocyclic azo dye, has been used in this work as reagent in the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II). This azo dye forms two water-soluble complexes with mercury(II), a dark red in neutral solution and a blue in alkaline medium with high molar absorptivities making the present method

sensitive enough in comparison to other heterocyclic azo dyes used in the determination of mercury(II).

THT complex of mercury(II) has been further utilised as analytical reagent for spectrophotometric determination of thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide. The analytical principle incorporated is the ligand exchange reaction in solution, in which these compounds decompose the complex quantitatively to release the dye.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 spectrophotometer with 10-mm matched glass cells was used for recording spectra and a Beckman pH meter was used for pH measurements.

A 1×10^{-3} M THT solution was prepared in double-distilled water; the solution was stable for several weeks. A standard solution of mercury(II) was prepared by dissolving metallic mercury in perchloric acid and was standardised gravimetrically³. Standard thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide solutions by dissolving appropriate amounts of analytical grade compounds in double-distilled water.

Phosphate buffer⁴ solution (pH 7.2) was prepared and 2 ml of this solution was used to bring the solutions for complexation reaction into the appropriate pH range.

Procedure :

Mercury(II) : To a suitable aliquot of sample containing 12–75 μg of mercury(II) add sufficient excess of THT solution (10 molar times) followed by phosphate buffer (2 ml) or to an aliquot containing 12–67.5 μg of mercury(II), excess THT (20 molar times) was added followed by 0.04 N sodium carbonate solution (4 ml). The solution was diluted to 25 ml with water and the absorbance measured at 550 nm or 633 nm against the reagent blank.

Thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide : To a solution containing 75 μg of mercury(II) was added 1×10^{-3} M THT solution (5 ml) followed by thiosulphate (0.2–1.57 ppm), thiourea (0.09–1.14 ppm) or thiosemicarbazide (0.11–1.27 ppm). The phosphate buffer solution (2 ml) was then added and diluted to 25 ml with water. The absorbance was measured against the reagent blank (5 ml of 1×10^{-3} M THT + 2 ml of phosphate buffer diluted to 25 ml). The difference between the absorbance of the complex before and after addition of thio compounds and the reagent blank is proportional to the concentration of the thio compounds.

Results and Discussion

Mercury(II) combines with THT to give two water-soluble complexes, a dark red in neutral solution having λ_{max} at 550 nm and a blue complex in alkaline medium having λ_{max} at 633 nm

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(Fig. 1). The absorbance is pH-dependent and is maximal at pH 6.8–7.9 for the dark red complex while the blue one is formed at pH

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of HgII-THT complexes at different pH, $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}=8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $\text{THT}=4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.

above 10.6. Subsequent studies on the dark-red complex have been carried out at neutral pH using 2 ml of the phosphate buffer. The blue complex formed at pH above 10.6 has been studied using 4 ml of a 0.04 N sodium carbonate solution. Some transition metals also produce colour with this reagent at pH 7.2. However, most of the common metals do not interfere when the procedure is followed at pH above 10.6, making the method highly selective. Most of the metals either do not develop colour with THT at high pH and if so, they absorb below 580 nm. Mercury(II) and indium(III) complexes absorb at 633 nm and 5 ppm of indium(III) has been masked using sulphide ions.

Physicochemical characteristics of the mercury(II)-THT complexes: Absorbance data recorded for a series of solution containing $8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ mercury(II) and varying amounts of reagent showed that at least 4 and 10 times molar excess of THT are required for full complexation for dark-red and blue coloured complexes respectively. The concentration ranges over which Beer's law obeyed are upto 3.8 and $3.63 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and the optimum concentration ranges for the accurate determination of metal ion are 0.48–3.0 and 0.48–2.7 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for dark-red and blue complexes respectively. The compositions of the complexes are 1:2 (red) and 1:3 (blue) (metal-ligand) as determined by Job's method of continuous variations. The complexes were not extractable in non-aqueous organic solvents showing thereby their ionic character. Sandell's sensitivities of the colour reactions are 0.0038 and 0.0030 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Hg, molar absorptivities (ϵ) 5.28×10^4 and $6.69 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The mean absorbances of solutions containing 1.6 ppm of mercury(II) were 0.422 and 0.535 (1-cm cell, 8 replicates) with

standard deviations of 0.004 and 0.0085 for the dark-red and blue complexes respectively.

To determine the stoichiometry of the decomposition behaviour of the mercury complex with thiosulphate, thiourea or thiosemicarbazide a mole-ratio study was made at pH 7.2. Varying volumes of standard solutions of thiosulphate, thiourea or thiosemicarbazide were added to a fixed amount of mercury-THT complex. The decrease in absorbance reached a maximum at mole ratio 1:1, thus displacing THT ions completely from the mercury-THT complex.

Effect of diverse ions on the determination of mercury(II): In the final solution at pH 7.2, fluoride, chloride, bromide, nitrite, nitrate, acetate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, borate, phosphate, sulphide, sulphate, alkaline earths, lanthanides, Al, V, Mo, W, Au and platinum metals did not interfere at all. However, iodide, thiosulphate, thiourea, thiosemicarbazide, cyanide, EDTA, acetylacetone, Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Ag^{I} and Pb^{II} interfered seriously; while thiocyanate (800 ppm), In^{III} , Bi^{III} , Sb^{III} (40, masked by sulphide ions) and Th^{IV} (50, masked by fluoride) were tolerated.

When the procedure was followed at pH 10.6, iodide, thiosulphate, thiourea, thiosemicarbazide, cyanide and EDTA interfered seriously, while chloride, nitrate, acetate, borate, phosphate, sulphite, sulphate, alkaline earths, lanthanides, aluminium, vanadium(V), molybdenum(VI), tungsten(VI), gold and platinum metals did not interfere (precipitates formed, if any, were removed by centrifugation). For other ions, the tolerance limits defined as the concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in the final solution) causing a deviation of less than $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance, were: fluoride (800), bromide (500), thiocyanate (500), citrate (450), tartrate (800), oxalate (500), sulphide (150), manganese(III) (25), Fe^{II} (20), Co^{II} (20), Ni^{II} (25), Cu^{II} (40), Ag^{I} (40), Pb^{II} (30), In^{III} (5, masked by 50 ppm sulphide), Sb^{III} (15), Bi^{III} (15), Th^{IV} (40) and U^{VI} (40).

Determination of thiosulphate, thiourea or thiosemicarbazide: The suppression of the colour of the mercury(II)-THT complex by thiosulphate, thiourea or thiosemicarbazide were studied by taking an aliquot of mercury(II) in the range 12–75 μg , adding 5 ml of $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ THT solution and varying the concentration of thio compounds in a total volume of 25 ml. Beer's law ranges for thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide were 0–1.9, 0–1.35, and 0–1.40 ppm respectively. Using the particular conditions adopted for the determination of mercury(II), 0.2–1.57 ppm of thiosulphate, 0.09–1.14 ppm of thiourea or 0.11–1.27 ppm of thiosemicarbazide could be accurately determined. These compounds were also determined by reacting them with an excess mercury(II) and then determining the unreacted mercury(II) with THT. The results showed reasonable reproducibility.

Effect of various anions in the determination of thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide: It

was found that iodide, cyanide, EDTA, acetylacetone also decomposed the mercury(II)–THT complex along with thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide, hence these interfered seriously in their determinations. The limits of other anions which did not cause a deviation of more than $\pm 2\%$ were chloride, bromide, nitrate, acetate and phosphate (upto 2000 ppm); fluoride, nitrite, oxalate, citrate and tartrate (1000); sulphide and thiocyanate (500). These are the limits of almost the same order as reported for the determination of mercury(II).

Conclusion: Thiosulphate reacts with cyanide in presence of copper(II) to form thiocyanate which can be determined as iron(III) thiocyanate complex at 496 nm⁸. Thiosulphate can also be oxidised by ferric ion to tetrathionate and excess of ferric ions is determined photometrically as thiocyanate complex⁹. Some other methods known are by extraction of thiosulphate with basic dyes, viz. rhodamine G and crystal violet⁷ in benzene and nitrobenzene 3 : 1 or 4 : 1 at 536 and 600 nm respectively. However, thiosulphate has also been determined indirectly by ligand exchange reaction, using mercury(II)–diphenylcarbazone⁸ and mercuric chloranilate⁹; comparatively the present method is highly sensitive where 0.20–1.57 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of thiosulphate could be accurately determined.

Colorimetric methods based on colour formation with pentacyanoammonioferrate are sensitive to 1 ppm of thiourea¹⁰. Thiourea reacts with nitrous acid to form thiocyanate which is measured as iron(III) thiocyanate at 455 nm and 4–32 ppm of thiourea is determined by this method. Sodium nitroprusside gives red-pink colour with ammoniacal solution of thiosemicarbazide which changes to stable intense red-violet colour after addition of

acetic acid¹¹. But this is a macro-test and if less than 100 μg of thiosemicarbazide is present, the colour changes to yellowish, green and then to reddish violet¹² after 2–3 min. Another method for thiosemicarbazide is based on the reaction with glyoxylic acid in which 0.9–15 μg of thiosemicarbazide is determined at 285 nm¹³. The present methods for thiourea and thiosemicarbazide are much simple and sensitive, where, 0.09–1.14 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of thiourea or 0.11–1.27 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of thiosemicarbazide can be accurately determined.

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